

DEVELOPMENT, UTILIZATION, AND NUTRITIONAL VALUE OF SUPPLEMENTED TILAPIA (*Oreochromis niloticus*) FLOUR PASTRY PRODUCTS

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the development and nutritional assessment of supplemented tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) flour pastry products, focusing on caramel tart, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas. The study aimed to innovate pastry recipes by incorporating tilapia flour, which was prepared through a process of cleaning, steaming, and grinding tilapia fish. The pastry products were evaluated for sensory attributes such as appearance, aroma, taste, and texture by 100 respondents across various age groups, using a five-point hedonic scale. Results indicated high consumer acceptability, with caramel tart scoring the highest in taste. Nutritional analysis of the pastries revealed significant levels of crude protein and fat, particularly in the yema empanaditas, which had a protein content of 15.07%. Shelf-life assessment showed that the pastries could maintain quality for several days at room temperature, with enhanced preservation in sealed containers. The findings suggest that tilapia flour can be effectively used in pastry production, offering a nutritious and appealing food option. This study emphasizes the potential for creating diverse and economically viable food products from fish flour, promoting dietary diversity, and supporting the economic development of tilapia farming communities.

Keywords: *Tilapia, Pastry products, caramel tart, coconut dumplings, yema empanaditas, sensory evaluation, consumer acceptability*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines, known for its hospitality and natural beauty, is home to a diverse array of aquatic species, many of which are vital to both the economy and cultural practices. The nation's rivers and coastal regions are not only tourist attractions but also crucial habitats for various fish species. In the City of Ilagan, local fishermen have harnessed technology to cultivate Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in man-made ponds, increasing their availability for commercial and personal use.

The Philippines predominantly cultures three tilapia species: Nile tilapia, Mozambique tilapia (*Oreochromis mossambicus*), and Blue tilapia (*Oreochromis aureus*). With production levels rising annually, tilapia has become a key aquaculture species, particularly in Region 2, where it is mainly consumed fresh, with minimal processing into other products (Department of Agriculture - Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources, 2001).

Dhanapal et al. (2010) have demonstrated that fresh tilapia meat is suitable for developing ready-to-eat and value-added products, including pastries. This research aims to explore the potential of tilapia meat as a primary ingredient in pastry products, thereby enhancing their nutritional value and acceptability.

Nile tilapia, a freshwater fish native to Africa, has become a global favorite due to its versatility and nutritional benefits. It is a popular Filipino dish, often grilled, broiled, steamed, or baked. Nile tilapia is an excellent source of protein, crude fat, crude protein, vitamins, minerals, polyunsaturated fatty acids, and omega-3 fatty acids, with lower mercury levels compared to other fish. Integrating tilapia into pastry products offers nutritious and affordable options for meals and snacks, potentially reducing malnutrition and unemployment by providing essential nutrients and economic opportunities (Izquierdo et al., 2004; Tafur, 2009; Cortés-Sánchez et al., 2019; WHO, 2020).

In the context of Abuan National High School in Cabecera 27, City of Ilagan, the absence of a school canteen means that teachers and students often purchase snacks from outside, which are typically less nutritious. Moreover, many parents in Abuan seek additional livelihoods to support their children's education and meet daily needs. This situation inspired the researcher to develop nutritious food options using tilapia flour.

Borja and Gemora (2016) highlight the importance Filipinos place on preparing nutritious food, emphasizing the need for adequate nutrition to support growth, maintenance, and repair of cells and tissues. Given the widespread availability and affordability of tilapia, incorporating it into pastry products could address these nutritional needs while providing new economic opportunities.

The study focused on creating and evaluating tilapia-based pastry products—caramel tart, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas—in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, texture, and overall acceptability across various age groups. It also examined the nutritional value and shelf life of these products at room temperature. The

research aimed to meet the dual objectives of providing healthy snack options for students and teachers and offering sustainable livelihoods for local parents.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, fish and fishery products are the principal protein source for Filipinos, with an annual consumption of 37 kg per person, making up about 12% of total protein intake (BFAR, 2019). Protein from fish is crucial as it contributes significantly to the diet, supporting food security and nutrition (Farzana et al., 2014; Akinoso et al., 2010). In Africa, tilapia is a readily available protein source, accessible to many (Ande et al., 2012). Additionally, tilapia provides 23 grams of protein per 3-ounce serving, making it a valuable food for older adults to prevent age-related muscle loss (Rust, 2020).

The 2020-2025 Dietary Guidelines for Americans recommend consuming seafood twice a week to gain the health benefits associated with omega-3 fatty acids, which are found in tilapia. Omega-3s are linked to reduced risks of diseases such as hypertension, diabetes, and arthritis (Simopoulos, 2011). They also help lower triglyceride levels and increase good cholesterol, contributing to heart health (Hibbs et al., 2018).

The popularity of tilapia in the Philippines has soared, earning it the nickname "aquatic chicken" due to its bland flavor and rapid growth. The Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources has significantly contributed to this growth by promoting tilapia farming across the country, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, to support food security (Fitzsimmons, 2005; Manalili, 2020).

Tilapia's versatility extends beyond fresh consumption; it can be processed into various forms, including smoked, dried, and canned fish, with different preservation methods affecting its nutritional composition (Holma and Maalekuu, 2013). For instance, dried fish products like fish crackers and fish galletas are popular snacks in Asian countries, indicating the potential for developing similar products in the Philippines (Nurul et al., 2009; Taewee, 2011).

This research aimed to develop and assess tilapia-based pastry products to provide nutritious and appealing food options while supporting local economies through sustainable fish farming and food processing innovations. By leveraging tilapia's health benefits and availability, this study sought to enhance dietary nutrition and create new livelihood opportunities in the Philippines.

Research Questions

This study explored the development, utilization, and nutritional value of supplemented Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) flour Pastry Products. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the processes involved in developing tilapia pastry food products?
 - a. Caramel tart
 - b. Coconut dumplings

- c. Yema empanaditas
 2. What is the level of acceptability of Tilapia pastry products in terms of:
 - a. appearance /color
 - b. aroma
 - c. taste
 - d. texture
 3. What is the general level of acceptability of Tilapia pastry food products as evaluated by the following groups of respondents:
 - a. children
 - b. teenagers
 - c. adults
 - d. experts
 4. Is there a significant difference in the general acceptability of the following tilapia pastry food products a. Caramel tart, b. Coconut dumplings, c. Yema empanaditas across age groups?
 5. What is the nutritive value of Tilapia pastry food products?
 6. What is the shelf-life of tilapia pastry products at room temperature and number of days?
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METHODOLOGY

Materials

1. Tools and Equipment

As shown below, preparation tools and equipment were used during the study.

Table 1. Tools and Equipment used in the preparation of Tilapia pastry food products

DESCRIPTION					
Preparation Tools	Measuring Tools	Mixing Tools	Cutting Tools	Baking Tools	Equipment
Flour Sifter	Measuring spoons	Mixing Bowl small, medium, Large	Knife	Baking pan	Traditional stove (<i>kalang de kahoy</i>)
Spatula	Measuring cups	Wire whisk	Kitchen scissors	Tart molder	Meat grinder
Rolling pin		Ladle		Pastry brush	Steamer
Utility tray					Electric Oven

Ingredients

Table 2 shows the ingredients used in the production of Tilapia Pastry Food Products.

Table 2. The proportion of ingredients used in the preparation of Tilapia pastry food products

Ingredients For Dough	Caramel Tart	Coconut Dumplings	Yema Empanaditas
Tilapia Flour (Sifted)	1 Cup	1 Cup	1 Cup
All -Purpose Flour (Sifted)	1 Cup	1 Cup	1 Cup
Cold Butter Cup	8 Tablespoon	8 Tablespoon	8 Tables Spoon
Water	1 ½ Tablespoon	1 ½ Tablespoon	1 ½ Tablespoon
Vinegar	2 Teaspoon	2 Teaspoon	2 Teaspoon
Egg	1 Piece Medium	1 Piece Medium	1 Piece Medium
Salt	½ Teaspoon	½ Teaspoon	½ Teaspoon
	Caramel Filling	Coconut Filling	Yema Filling
	1/2 cup light brown sugar	½ cup grated coconut	¼ cup All- Purpose Flour
	1 cup Alaska evaporated milk	¼ cup light brown sugar	½ cup water
	1 tablespoon butter cup	¼ cup butter cup	1 small egg yolk
	4 tablespoon cornstarch		1/8 cup butter cup
	2 pieces medium egg		2/3 cups Alaska condensed milk

Developmental Procedure

To perform the research properly, the flow chart of the procedures in making *tilapia pastry food products* such as caramel tart, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas was consistently followed. The needed tools, materials equipment, and ingredients were prepared and followed by mixing the major ingredients, cooking, cooling, and packing.

The developmental procedure began with the preparation of tilapia flour, the preparation of dough for the caramel tart, coconut dumpling, and yema empanaditas, the preparation of three different fillings, making the caramel tart, coconut dumplings and yema empanaditas, and baking.

Preparation of Tilapia Flour

The preparation of tilapia flour began by first cleaning the Nile tilapia. The scales and visceral contents were removed using a sharp knife, and the gills and tail were cut off with kitchen scissors. The tilapia was then washed thoroughly with potable water. Next, six cups of water were poured into a steamer, and the tilapia was steamed for 20 minutes. After steaming, the fish was allowed to cool. Once cooled, the top skin was removed by hand, and the fish meat was collected, ensuring all bones and remaining skin were discarded. The collected fish meat was ground using a meat grinder until it resembled wet flour. This ground fish meat was then spread out for sun drying over 2-3 days. When it was partially dried, it was ground again to pulverize it further. The fish meat was then returned to the sun for additional drying, being stirred occasionally to ensure even dryness. Once the desired dryness was achieved, the tilapia flour was sifted using a sieve to make it fine. Finally, the produced tilapia flour was stored in a closed microwave container to maintain its dryness and protect it from moisture and contaminants. This method ensured that the flour remained protein-rich and suitable for various culinary applications.

Preparation of Caramel Tart

To begin the preparation, all necessary ingredients were measured. In a mixing bowl, 1 cup of tilapia flour, 1 cup of all-purpose flour, 8 tablespoons of cold butter, 1 ½ tablespoons of water, 2 teaspoons of vinegar, 1 medium egg, and ½ teaspoon of salt were combined. After mixing these ingredients, the dough was formed into a ball, covered with plastic wrap, and left to proof for 30 minutes.

Once proofed, the working surface was lightly dusted with a small amount of all-purpose flour, and the dough was kneaded until it became pliable. Using a rolling pin, the dough was flattened and portioned with a stainless glass, with each portion equivalent to 1 tablespoon. Boat-shaped tart molds were greased with a little butter, the dough portions were placed into the molds, and 1 teaspoon of caramel filling was added to each.

The oven was preheated to 180°C (355°F), and the tarts were baked for 10 minutes until cooked. After baking, the tarts were allowed to cool before being stored in a storage box.

Preparation of Caramel Filling

The preparation began by measuring all the needed ingredients. In a bowl, 1/2 cup of brown sugar, 1 cup of Alaska evaporated milk, 4 tablespoons of cornstarch, and 2 eggs were mixed using a wire whisk. A pan was placed over low heat, and butter was melted in the pan. The mixture was then poured into the pan, and stirring continued until it cooked and thickened. Once the caramel filling was cooked, it was allowed to cool before being used.

Preparation of Coconut Dumpling

The preparation began by measuring all the necessary ingredients. In a mixing bowl, 1 cup of tilapia flour, 1 cup of all-purpose flour, 8 tablespoons of cold butter, 1 ½ tablespoons of water, 2 teaspoons of vinegar, 1 medium egg, and ½ teaspoon of salt were combined. The mixed dough was formed into a ball, covered with plastic wrap, and left to proof for 30 minutes. After proofing, the working surface was lightly dusted with a small amount of all-purpose flour, and the dough was kneaded until it became pliable. Using a rolling pin, the dough was flattened and portioned using a stainless glass, with each portion equivalent to 1 tablespoon. Each portion was picked up with both palms, filled with 1 teaspoon of coconut filling, and folded to form a ball shape, similar to a ping-pong ball. The oven was preheated to 180°C (355°F), and the dough balls were baked for 10 minutes until cooked. After baking, the coconut dumplings were allowed to cool before being stored in a storage box.

Preparation of Coconut Filling

The preparation began by measuring the needed ingredients. A pan was placed over low heat, and the butter was added, allowing it to melt. Once the butter had melted, the grated coconut and light brown sugar were added to the pan. The mixture was stirred continuously until it was cooked through. After cooking, the coconut filling was allowed to cool before being used.

Preparation of Yema Empanaditas

The preparation began by measuring all the needed ingredients. In a mixing bowl, 1 cup of tilapia flour, 1 cup of all-purpose flour, 8 tablespoons of cold butter, 1 ½ tablespoons of water, 2 teaspoons of vinegar, 1 medium egg, and ½ teaspoon of salt were combined. The dough was then formed into a ball, covered with plastic wrap, and allowed to proof for 30 minutes.

After proofing, the working surface was lightly dusted with a small amount of all-purpose flour, and the dough was kneaded until it reached a pliable consistency. The dough was flattened with a rolling pin to approximately 1/8 inch thickness, and circles were cut out using a glass with a 2-inch diameter.

For each circle, half of the dough's circumference was estimated, and 1 teaspoon of yema filling was added. The dough was folded over the filling, and the edges were crimped with water and a fork to seal them securely.

The oven was preheated to 180°C (355°F), and the filled pastries were baked for approximately 10 minutes, or until they were fully cooked. Once baked, the yema empanaditas were allowed to cool before being transferred to a storage box.

Preparation of Yema Filling

The preparation began by measuring all the needed ingredients. The flour was placed in a pan over low heat and toasted until it turned light brown, which took about 5 minutes. Once toasted, the flour was transferred to a bowl.

In a separate pan, the butter was melted over low heat. The mixture of condensed milk, toasted flour, egg, and water was then poured into the pan with the melted butter. The mixture was stirred continuously with a ladle until it thickened to the point where it could easily be molded into shapes. Once the mixture reached the desired consistency, it was set aside to cool.

Preparation of Tilapia Pastry Food Products (a) Caramel tart (b) Coconut dumplings (c) Yema empanaditas

A flow diagram of the procedure for making the Tilapia Pastry Food Products (Caramel tart, Coconut dumplings, and Yema empanaditas) is shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Flow Diagram of the Procedure for Making Tilapia Pastry Food Products

Data Gathering Instrument

The study used a modified instrument from the 2017 study of Prof. Catherine M. Aggabao titled “Macaroons with Shoots from Different Species of Bamboo” at Isabela State University Ilagan Campus. The modified instrument consisted of evaluation criteria on the utilization and nutritional value of tilapia pastry products. The data were gathered through the administered questionnaire checklist to the respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct the study through sensory evaluation was requested with the respondents consisting of Children (7-12), Teenagers (13-18), Adults (19-above), and Teachers. After permission was granted, administration of the questionnaires followed. Directions concerning the completion of the questionnaires was discussed by the researcher to the evaluators personally. Copies of the questionnaire checklist were retrieved after they were completed by the respondents. The sensory evaluation through a questionnaire checklist was used to gather information about the utilization and nutritional value of tilapia pastry food products. The observation method was applied to determine the changes in the appearance/color, aroma, taste, and texture.

Sensory Evaluation

The finished products were evaluated by one hundred (100) evaluators from varied age groups who were selected and properly oriented on what and how to evaluate the products using the scorecard with the sample code.

The tilapia pastry products were served. Each evaluator was asked to taste the samples from each food product. Data on the appearance/color, aroma, taste, texture, and general acceptability of each pastry food product were collected, interpreted, and analyzed.

To determine the acceptability of tilapia pastry products made from Nile tilapia flour in terms of appearance/color, aroma, taste, and texture, a score sheet and a five-point hedonic scale with descriptive rating were used.

Scale	Numeric Rating	Descriptive Rating
5	4.50-5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	3.50-4.49	Moderately Acceptable
3	2.50-3.49	Acceptable
2	1.50-2.49	Fairly Acceptable
1	1.00-1.49	Not Acceptable

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Product Development

The development of tilapia flour-based pastries involved several meticulous stages. Initially, fresh tilapia was prepared, thoroughly cleaned, and washed under running water. The cleaned tilapia was then steamed until fully cooked, ensuring easy separation of the meat. After steaming, the fish was allowed to cool, and the skin was removed. The meat was carefully collected, separated from bones and other inedible parts, and ground to a fine consistency. This ground meat was sun-dried until completely dehydrated and then pulverized into fine flour. The flour was sifted to achieve a uniform texture and subsequently stored in airtight containers.

For dough preparation, precise measurements of tilapia flour and other ingredients were taken, mixed to form a dough, and allowed to rest and rise during the proofing stage. The dough was dusted lightly to prevent sticking, kneaded until smooth and elastic, and portioned for individual pastries. The filling preparation entailed measuring, cooking, and cooling the ingredients as per the recipe.

Different samples were created to determine the optimal recipe for tilapia pastry products, varying the measurements of Nile tilapia flour to ensure the best quality and acceptability. The best-performing recipe was then used to make caramel tarts, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas. This comprehensive process led to the development of high-quality tilapia flour-based pastries that were standardized for consistent production.

Figure 2. Fresh Tilapias are developed into Pastry Products

Figure 3. Grinding/Pulverizing the dried fish meat

Figure 4. Developed Pastry Products (Caramel Tart, Coconut Dumplings, and Yema Empanaditas) made of Tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*)

Acceptability of Tilapia Pastry Food Products

Table 3. Level of acceptability of Tilapia pastry food products in terms of appearance/color, aroma, taste, and texture.

Variant	Criteria	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
<i>Caramel Tart</i>	Appearance	4.67	0.49	Highly Acceptable
	Aroma	4.52	0.67	Highly Acceptable
	Taste	4.78	0.41	Highly Acceptable
	Texture	4.61	0.57	Highly Acceptable
Average		4.64	0.31	Highly Acceptable
<i>Coconut Dumpling</i>	Appearance	4.46	0.67	Moderately acceptable
	Aroma	4.37	0.75	Moderately acceptable
	Taste	4.57	0.59	Highly Acceptable
	Texture	4.58	0.57	Highly Acceptable
Average		4.49	0.38	Moderately acceptable
<i>Yema Empanaditas</i>	Appearance	4.63	0.52	Highly Acceptable
	Aroma	4.51	0.59	Highly Acceptable
	Taste	4.70	0.48	Highly Acceptable
	Texture	4.31	0.70	Moderately acceptable
Average		4.54	0.34	Highly Acceptable

The table presents the level of acceptability of tilapia pastry products among the four groups of respondents in terms of appearance/color, aroma, taste, and texture.

The analysis of respondents' perceptions regarding the acceptability of Tilapia pastry products reveals distinct patterns across three variants: Caramel Tart, Coconut dumplings, and Yema Empanaditas.

For the *Caramel Tart* variant, respondents consistently rated it highly acceptable across all criteria, with mean scores ranging from 4.52 to 4.78. Notably, it garnered particularly strong approval for taste, with a mean score of 4.78, indicating its exceptional flavor.

Conversely, the *Coconut Dumpling* variant, while still moderately acceptable overall with an average mean score of 4.49, received slightly lower ratings for appearance and aroma, with mean scores of 4.46 and 4.37 respectively. However, it excelled in taste and texture, with mean scores of 4.57 and 4.58 respectively.

Lastly, the *Yema Empanaditas* variant exhibited consistently high mean scores across appearance, aroma, and taste, with scores above 4.5, indicating high acceptability. However, its texture received a moderately acceptable rating, with a mean score of 4.31. Despite this, the overall average score of 4.54 suggests that Yema Empanaditas remains highly acceptable.

Overall, the findings underscore the favorable reception of Tilapia pastry products among respondents, with variations observed in specific attributes across different product variants.

General Acceptability Rating of Tilapia Pastry Food Products across Groups of Respondents

Table 4. The general level of acceptability of *Caramel tart* as evaluated by children, teenagers, adults, and experts

Respondents	Product	Criteria	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
Children	Caramel Tart	Appearance	4.48	0.59	Moderately acceptable
		Aroma	4.52	0.65	Highly Acceptable
		Taste	4.60	0.50	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	4.36	0.70	moderately acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.49	0.24	moderately acceptable
Teenagers		Appearance	4.68	0.48	Highly Acceptable
		Aroma	4.40	0.71	moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.80	0.41	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	4.44	0.58	moderately acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.58	0.28	Highly Acceptable
Adults		Appearance	4.68	0.48	Highly Acceptable
		Aroma	4.44	0.77	moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.76	0.44	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	4.72	0.46	Highly Acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.65	0.31	Highly Acceptable
Experts	Appearance	4.84	0.37	Highly Acceptable	
	Aroma	4.72	0.54	Highly Acceptable	
	Taste	4.96	0.20	Highly Acceptable	
	Texture	4.92	0.28	Highly Acceptable	
	Overall Mean	4.86	0.30	Highly Acceptable	

The analysis of respondents' evaluations regarding the acceptability of Tilapia pastry food products specifically **Caramel Tart** reveals variations in perceptions across different age groups and expert opinions.

Children's responses indicate a moderately acceptable perception of the Caramel Tart variant, with mean scores ranging from 4.36 to 4.60 across appearance, aroma, taste, and texture. Despite some variability, the overall mean score for children is 4.49, suggesting a moderate level of acceptability among this demographic.

Teenagers, on the other hand, rated the Caramel Tart variant more favorably, with mean scores ranging from 4.40 to 4.80 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.58 indicates a highly acceptable perception of the product, particularly in terms of appearance, taste, and overall acceptability.

Adult respondents rated the Caramel Tart variant similarly to teenagers, with mean scores ranging from 4.44 to 4.76 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.65 indicates a highly acceptable perception of the product, with particularly high ratings for taste and texture.

In contrast, *experts* evaluated the Caramel Tart variant even more positively, with mean scores ranging from 4.72 to 4.96 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.86 suggests a highly favorable perception of the product, with consistently high ratings across all evaluated aspects.

Overall, while there are slight variations in the perception of Caramel Tart among different respondent groups, the general trend indicates a high level of acceptability across all demographics, with experts showing the most positive evaluations.

Table 5. The general level of acceptability of *Coconut Dumplings* as evaluated by children, teenagers, adults, and experts

Respondents	Product	Criteria	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
Children	Coconut Dumpling	Appearance	4.28	0.74	Moderately acceptable
		Aroma	4.20	0.82	Moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.40	0.64	Moderately acceptable
		Texture	4.60	0.50	Highly Acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.37	0.31	Moderately acceptable
Teenagers		Appearance	4.28	0.74	Moderately acceptable
		Aroma	4.28	0.74	Moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.64	0.49	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	4.68	0.48	Highly Acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.47	0.33	Moderately acceptable
Adults		Appearance	4.48	0.65	Moderately acceptable
		Aroma	4.24	0.78	Moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.36	0.70	Moderately acceptable
		Texture	4.28	0.74	Moderately acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.34	0.37	Moderately acceptable
Experts	Appearance	4.80	0.41	Highly Acceptable	
	Aroma	4.76	0.52	Highly Acceptable	
	Taste	4.88	0.33	Highly Acceptable	
	Texture	4.76	0.43	Highly Acceptable	
	Overall Mean	4.80	0.35	Highly Acceptable	

The respondents' perceptions regarding the acceptability of **Coconut Dumplings** show varying perspectives across different age groups and expert opinions.

Children provided moderately acceptable ratings for the Coconut Dumpling variant, with mean scores ranging from 4.20 to 4.60 across appearance, aroma, taste, and texture. Despite the variability in ratings, the overall mean score for children is 4.37, suggesting a moderately acceptable perception among this demographic.

Similarly, *teenagers* rated the Coconut Dumpling variant as moderately acceptable, with mean scores ranging from 4.28 to 4.68 across the criteria. However,

their overall mean score of 4.47 indicates a slightly higher level of acceptability compared to children.

Adult respondents also rated the Coconut Dumpling variant as moderately acceptable, with mean scores ranging from 4.24 to 4.48 across the criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.34 aligns with the perceptions of children and teenagers, indicating a consistent level of acceptability across different age groups.

In contrast, *experts* evaluated the Coconut Dumpling variant more positively, with mean scores ranging from 4.76 to 4.88 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.80 suggests a highly favorable perception of the product, with consistently high ratings across all evaluated aspects.

Overall, while there are variations in the perception of Coconut Dumplings among different respondent groups, the general trend indicates a moderately acceptable level of acceptability across all demographics, with experts providing the most positive evaluations.

Table 6. The general level of acceptability of *Yema Empanaditas* as evaluated by children, teenagers, adults, and experts

Respondents	Product	Criteria	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
Children	Yema Empanaditas	Appearance	4.64	0.57	Highly Acceptable
		Aroma	4.44	0.58	Moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.60	0.50	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	3.92	0.70	Moderately acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.40	0.31	Moderately acceptable
Teenagers		Appearance	4.44	0.51	Moderately acceptable
		Aroma	4.36	0.58	Moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.80	0.41	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	4.44	0.58	Moderately acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.53	0.19	Highly Acceptable
Adults		Appearance	4.56	0.58	Highly Acceptable
		Aroma	4.36	0.70	Moderately acceptable
		Taste	4.48	0.59	Moderately acceptable
		Texture	4.08	0.76	Moderately acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.37	0.36	Moderately acceptable
Experts		Appearance	4.88	0.33	Highly Acceptable
		Aroma	4.80	0.41	Highly Acceptable
		Taste	4.92	0.28	Highly Acceptable
		Texture	4.80	0.41	Highly Acceptable
		Overall Mean	4.85	0.27	Highly Acceptable

The table presents the level of acceptability of the four groups of respondents of *Yema Empanaditas*.

Children rated the Yema Empanaditas variant as moderately acceptable, with mean scores ranging from 3.92 to 4.64 across appearance, aroma, taste, and texture. While

aspects like appearance and taste were highly acceptable, texture received a lower rating, contributing to an overall mean score of 4.40, indicating a moderately acceptable perception among this demographic.

Conversely, *teenagers* perceived the Yema Empanaditas variant more favorably, with mean scores ranging from 4.36 to 4.80 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.53 suggests a highly acceptable perception of the product, particularly in terms of taste, which received the highest rating among all criteria.

Adult respondents rated the Yema Empanaditas variant similarly to children, with mean scores ranging from 4.08 to 4.56 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.37 aligns with the perceptions of children, indicating a consistent level of moderately acceptable acceptability across different age groups.

In contrast, *experts* evaluated the Yema Empanaditas variant more positively, with mean scores ranging from 4.80 to 4.92 across criteria. Their overall mean score of 4.85 suggests a highly favorable perception of the product, with consistently high ratings across all evaluated aspects, particularly in appearance, aroma, taste, and texture.

Overall, while there are variations in the perception of Yema Empanaditas among different respondent groups, the general trend indicates a moderately to a highly acceptable level of acceptability across all demographics, with experts providing the most positive evaluations.

Comparison in the Acceptability of Three Tilapia Pastry Food Products

Table 5. Comparison in the General Acceptability of Tilapia Pastry Food Products

Food products	F-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Remarks
Caramel Tart	7.65	0.00	p-value < 0.05	Reject Ho	Difference is significant
Coconut Dumpling	9.45	0.00	p-value < 0.05	Reject Ho	Difference is significant
Yema Empanaditas	14.37	0.00	p-value < 0.05	Reject Ho	Difference is significant

Table 6. Post-hoc analysis using Tukey HSD on the significant difference of the respondents' general acceptability of Tilapia Pastry Food Products

Dependent Variable	Groups		Mean Difference	p-value
Caramel Tart	Children	Teenagers	-0.09	0.68
		Adults	-0.16	0.20
		Experts	-0.37*	0.00
	Teenagers	Children	0.09	0.68
		Adults	-0.07	0.82
		Experts	-0.28*	0.00
	Adults	Children	0.16	0.20
		Teenagers	0.07	0.82
		Experts	-0.21	0.05
	Experts	Children	0.37*	0.00
		Teenager	0.28*	0.00
		Adults	0.21	0.05
Coconut Dumpling	Children	Teenagers	-0.10	0.73
		Adults	0.03	0.99
		Experts	-0.43*	0.00
	Teenager	Children	0.10	0.73
		Adults	0.13	0.54
		Experts	-0.33*	0.00
	Adults	Children	-0.03	0.99
		Teenagers	-0.13	0.54
		Experts	-0.46*	0.00
	Experts	Children	0.43*	0.00
		Teenager	0.33*	0.00
		Adults	0.46*	0.00
Yema Empanaditas	Children	Teenagers	-0.13	0.39
		Adults	0.03	0.98
		Experts	-0.45*	0.00
	Teenager	Children	0.13	0.39
		Adults	0.16	0.21
		Experts	-0.32*	0.00
	Adults	Children	-0.03	0.98
		Teenagers	-0.16	0.21
		Experts	-0.48*	0.00
	Experts	Children	0.45*	0.00
		Teenager	0.32*	0.00
		Adults	0.48*	0.00

The table presents the analysis of the significant difference in the general acceptability of the three tilapia pastry products across children, teenagers, adults, and

experts. It also includes a Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey HSD to determine which among the groups differ in perceptions.

The analysis reveals a significant difference in the general acceptability of the three tilapia pastry food products (Caramel Tart, Coconut Dumpling, and Yema Empanaditas) across age groups, as indicated by the obtained F-values and p-values

For *Caramel Tart*, the F-value of 7.65 with a p-value less than 0.05 indicates a rejection of the null hypothesis, signifying a significant difference in acceptability across age groups. Specifically, post-hoc analysis using Tukey HSD reveals significant differences between children and experts, as well as between teenagers and experts, with experts rating the Caramel Tart significantly higher in general acceptability compared to both children and teenagers

Similarly, for *Coconut Dumpling*, the F-value of 9.45 with a p-value less than 0.05 signifies a significant difference in acceptability across age groups. Post-hoc analysis shows significant differences between children and experts, as well as between teenagers and experts, with experts rating the Coconut Dumpling significantly higher in general acceptability compared to both children and teenagers.

For *Yema Empanaditas*, the F-value of 14.37 with a p-value less than 0.05 also indicates a significant difference in acceptability across age groups. Post-hoc analysis reveals significant differences between children and experts, between teenagers and experts, and between adults and experts, with experts rating Yema Empanaditas significantly higher in general acceptability compared to all other age groups.

In summary, the F-values and p-values confirm significant differences in the general acceptability of all three tilapia pastry food products across age groups, with experts consistently rating them higher compared to children, teenagers, and adults.

Table 6. Nutritive Value of Tilapia Pastry Food Products Report of Analysis

Lab. No	Sample Description	Crude Protein	Crude Fat	Moisture
		%	%	%
FT-24-0005	Yema empanaditas, 1	15.07	15.09	25.48
FT-24-0006	Coconut dumplings, 2	13.46	14.10	19.74
FT-24-0007	Caramel tart, 3	11.49	14.45	33.15

Note: 1) Sample will be kept only for a month from the date received; 2) environmental conditions, Temperature: 25 Degrees °C±3, Relative Humidity: 40-60%

Table 6 shows the result of the Analysis of Tilapia pastry food products conducted by the Department of Agriculture Regional Field Office No.02 Tuguegarao City, Cagayan Integrated Laboratory Division with laboratory number FT24- 005-007 the requested service/s Crude Fat, Crude Protein and Moisture.

The *Caramel Tart* based on the test semi-automatic Kjeldahl method using the Reference Method (AOAC Official Method 984.13) has a Crude Protein of 11.49%; ANKOM Filter Bag Technique using the Reference Method (In-house method) has Crude Fat of 14.45%; the Gravimetric Method using the Reference Method (AOAC Official Method 934.0) has moisture of 33.15%.

The *Coconut Dumplings* based on the test semi-automatic Kjeldahl method using the Reference Method (AOAC Official Method 984.13) have a Crude Protein of 13.46%; ANKOM Filter Bag Technique using the Reference Method (In-house method) has Crude Fat of 14.10 %; the Gravimetric Method using the Reference Method (AOAC Official Method 934.0) has moisture of 19.74%.

The *Yema Empanaditas* based on the test semi-automatic Kjeldahl method using the Reference Method (AOAC Official Method 984.13) has a Crude Protein of 15.07%; ANKOM Filter Bag Technique using the Reference Method (In-house method) has Crude Fat 15.09 %; the Gravimetric Method using the Reference Method (AOAC Official Method 934.0) has moisture of 25.08%.

Shelf-Life of Tilapia Pastry Products at Normal Room Temperature

An 11-day observation was conducted on caramel tart, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas stored at normal room temperature. The following observations were noted:

- Day 1: The caramel tart, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas had perfect appearance, aroma, taste, and texture.
- Day 2: The pastries maintained their perfect appearance, aroma, taste, and texture.
- Day 3: When exposed to open air, the crusts of all three pastries became crumbly and hard.
- Day 4: The crusts remained hard.
- Day 5: No additional changes were observed.
- Day 6: No changes occurred.
- Day 7: No changes were observed.
- Day 8: No changes were observed.
- Day 9: The aroma decreased, with a reduction in the initial fishy smell.
- Day 10: The crusts of the pastries hardened further.
- Day 11: The crusts maintained their color and firmness, but an unpleasant smell indicating spoilage was present in the fillings.

Shelf-Life of Tilapia Pastry Products in Normal Room Temperature in a Closed Microwave Container

A five-day observation was also conducted on caramel tart, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas stored at normal room temperature in tightly sealed containers. The following observations were noted:

Day 1: The pastries had perfect appearance, aroma, taste, and texture.

Day 2: The pastries maintained their normal condition.

Day 3: The crusts of the pastries reduced in firmness.

Day 4: The crusts became soft.

Day 5:

- The caramel tart's crust became soft, and white molds with discoloration formed on the filling.
- The coconut dumpling's crust became soft, with a white spider-web-like structure forming between the coconut filling and producing a foul odor.
- The yema empanaditas' crust became soft, and the filling became moist and produced a foul odor indicating spoilage.

Conclusions

The development and evaluation of tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) flour-based pastry products, namely caramel tarts, coconut dumplings, and yema empanaditas, prove their high nutritional value and general acceptability across various demographics. The process of creating these pastries ensures the production of high-quality, standardized products. The acceptability ratings indicate an extreme preference for the caramel tart variant, while all three products received favorable evaluations, especially from expert respondents. Nutritional analysis confirmed that these pastries are rich in protein and provide essential nutrients, aligning with the benefits of fish consumption in the diet. Shelf-life studies highlighted the importance of proper storage to maintain quality and prevent spoilage. Overall, tilapia pastry products offer a nutritious, appealing food option with broad acceptability, emphasizing their potential as innovative and healthy additions to the culinary market.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, this study has the following recommendations:

1. Recipes should be continuously refined to enhance the sensory attributes of tilapia pastry products. The focus should be on improving aspects such as appearance, aroma, taste, and texture to ensure consistent high acceptability across all variants.
2. The consumers should be educated about the nutritional value of tilapia pastry products, emphasizing their high protein content and essential nutrient profile. This

should be done through packaging labels, marketing materials, or nutritional awareness campaigns.

3. Marketing strategies should be tailored to target specific demographic groups based on their preferences and perceptions. For instance, the unique flavors and textures of each variant should be highlighted to appeal to diverse consumer segments.
4. There should be clear guidelines on proper storage to maintain product quality and prolong shelf-life. This may include recommending airtight containers or refrigeration to prevent moisture absorption and spoilage.
5. Continuous innovation in tilapia pastry product development like exploring new flavors, fillings, and pastry formats should be encouraged. This could involve collaborating with culinary experts or conducting consumer surveys to identify emerging trends and preferences.
6. Implementation of stringent quality control measures throughout the production process to ensure consistency and adherence to standards should be in place. Regular sensory evaluations and nutritional analyses can help maintain product quality and meet consumer expectations.
7. Foster collaboration between the academe, industry, and government agencies (DOST, DA, and DTI) to further research on tilapia pastry products. This could include investigating innovative processing techniques, exploring novel ingredients, and evaluating the health benefits of consuming these products

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher's unwavering commitment to ethical standards is evident in the meticulous adherence to principles of integrity, respect, and responsibility towards participants. Prior to the study, informed consent was obtained, ensuring participants' understanding of the research purpose and procedures, while maintaining confidentiality and anonymity throughout. By avoiding conflicts of interest, plagiarism, and bias, the researcher upheld the study's credibility and trustworthiness and ensured that the findings were used solely for research purposes, reflecting a dedication to ethical research conduct.

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